

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

INFLUENCE OF THE SUN ON THE EARTH'S CRUST AND ON STRUCTURING OF WATER MOLECULES

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Abstract

Solar radiation breaks hydrogen bonds between water molecules, which destroys water clusters and increases their chemical reactivity. Because of anisotropy of the solar influence, the rates of hydrolytic reactions depend on geometric shape of a reaction solution, its position in space and change during the day depending on the position of the Sun in the sky. We have obtained experimental evidence that the Sun influences the structuring of water molecules not only directly, but also through the Earth's crust, which emits some secondary radiation from underground. This underground radiation also destroys water clusters and accelerates hydrolytic reactions. Due to the heterogeneity of the Earth's crust, the intensity and direction of the impact coming from underground are not the same in different places on the Earth. For example, at two locations 100 meters apart, the hydrolysis of triethyl phosphite in multidirectional NMR-tubes can differ significantly in the reaction rate and its distribution between different directions. After sunset, underground radiation does not disappear but continues for some time, gradually relaxing. This explains why at midnight the hydrolysis rates in multidirectional NMR-tubes slow down but do not become equal. This fundamental phenomenon requires detailed study in different places on Earth.

Keywords: water; clusters; solar influence; earth's crust; hydrolysis

Introduction

Because of the ability of water molecules to form hydrogen bonds with each other, in bulk water all molecules are united by a common continuous three-dimensional network of hydrogen bonds [1], [2]. On mixing bulk water with organic solvents this network disintegrates with the formation of clusters $(H_2O)_n$ the size of which can vary from a few water molecules to several hundred [3]. Large clusters are much less chemically reactive because their hydroxyl groups ($-OH$) are involved in a large network of hydrogen bonds. In contrast, small clusters are much more reactive as they are unable to form three-dimensional structures and contain many free $-OH$ groups [1], [2].

We have recently discovered that the rate of hydrolysis of triethyl phosphite $((EtO)_3P)$ in acetonitrile can change by 200 times over the course of a year under the influence of the Sun. [4], [5] Such significant variations may be accounted for by the decomposition of water clusters by muons which are constantly generated in

the upper atmosphere by the solar wind. This is confirmed by the fact that the rate of hydrolysis of triethyl phosphite strongly slows down during solar eclipse. We observed this experimentally in August 2017. In addition, because muons are absorbed by buildings [6], the rate of this reaction in our experiments was always lower in the laboratory than in the open air.

Muon flux is anisotropic its direction and intensity depend on the position of the Sun in the sky and change during the day. For this reason the solar influence on the rate of hydrolysis of triethyl phosphite is strongly dependent on the geometry of the reaction solution and its position in space [7]. For example, in three 5 mm NMR-tubes directed North-South, East-West and Vertically the hydrolysis of triethyl phosphite in acetonitrile occurs at very different rates. At noon, when the Sun is at its zenith, the reaction in horizontal tubes can proceed much faster than in the vertical one, and at sunrise and sunset, when the Sun shines along the East-West line, the reaction rates become opposite, and hydrolysis occurs faster in the vertical tube. (Fig. 1)

Conversion rate in multidirectional NMR-tubes in July 2020. Reaction time 0.5h

At Noon 12.00-12.30

At Sunset 18.30-19.00

0 50% 100%

Fig. 1. Rates of hydrolysis of triethyl phosphite in July 2020 in multidirectional 5 mm NMR-tubes at Noon and at Sunset (reaction time 0.5h).

It was logical to assume that at night, when the Sun irradiates the opposite side of the Earth, it cannot influence water clusters, and the rates of this reaction in multidirectional NMR-tubes should become equal. However, experiments conducted at midnight in May and September 2023 unexpectedly showed the same rate

distribution as at noon, with only the hydrolysis rate decreased [8]. In the vertical tube hydrolysis proceeded much slower. (Fig. 2) This result can be explained by the presence of some kind of radiation from underground at midnight.

Conversion rate in multidirectional NMR-tubes at Night

May 2023. Reaction time 6h (00.00-06.00)

Fig. 2. Rates of hydrolysis of triethyl phosphite in multidirectional 5 mm NMR-tubes at Night in May 2023 (reaction time 6h).

Studying the daytime and nighttime rates of hydrolysis led to the discovery of an unknown influence of the Sun on the Earth.

Results and discussion

Repeated comparisons of daytime and nighttime rates of triethyl phosphite hydrolysis confirmed our initial observation that the rates of this reaction in multidirectional tubes decrease at night, but do not become equal and can differ depending on solar activity and the position of the Earth relative to the Sun. This points to the existence of not only the direct solar radiation reaching the reaction solution from the sky, but also some radiation coming from underground which should also be a result of solar influence. They both change the structuring and hydrolytic activity of water clusters, however, the mechanisms of solar influence on the day and night sides of the Earth must be different.

On the dayside of the Earth, the Sun may influence water through muons which reach the surface of the Earth and can penetrate to some depth underground. However, muons cannot penetrate the entire Earth, so the radiation from underground on the night side of the Earth must have another cause. It was logical to assume that if solar influence could modulate earthquakes in the crust of the Earth [9], then it could also cause some processes there that emit radiation. This radiation cannot be generated in the Earth's crust at night, when the Sun irradiates the opposite side of the Earth. However, if underground radiation can be generated during the day under the direct influence of the Sun, then it can be assumed that after sunset this radiation can continue to be emitted at night with gradually weakening intensity. This must be a cyclic process that is repeated every day after sunrise. If this is true, then at midday the structuring of water clusters should be influenced by both external muons from the sky and internal radiation from underground.

It could also be assumed that due to the heterogeneity of the Earth's crust, the intensity of radiation coming out from underground is not the same everywhere and may cause different rates of hydrolytic processes in different places at noon. To test this experimentally, we decided to compare the rates of triethyl phosphite hydrolysis in multidirectional NMR-tubes at two locations, about 100 meters apart. This was carried out away from large buildings as they can absorb muons [6]. At noon, at such a distance between the two experiments, the external solar influence on them should be the same, so the difference in reaction rate can only arise from different underground influences. Since the solar influence on the multidirectional tubes strongly depends on the position of the Sun in the sky, measurements on different days were taken at the same time at noon. Initially, experimental evidences of the influence of underground radiation on water were obtained in Kyiv, and in 2023 they were confirmed in detail in Bremen at a distance of 1500 km at the same geographical latitude.

The results obtained in Bremen are presented in Figure 3. They were very informative and exceeded expectations. In two locations (A and B) at a distance of 100 meters from each other, the difference in the hydrolysis rates turned out to be very large and dynamically changing. This was also reflected in the distribution of rates between multidirectional NMR-tubes.

On September 21, the hydrolysis rate in vertical tubes differed by 4 times, but there was no difference between horizontal tubes. The relationships between horizontal and vertical tubes turned out to be opposite. In location A, the rate in the vertical tube was slightly less than in the horizontal tubes, and in location B, on the contrary, it was much greater.

Rates of hydrolysis on September 21, 2023. Reaction time 12.00-13.30

Fig. 3. Rates of triethyl phosphite hydrolysis in acetonitrile in multidirectional 5 mm NMR-tubes. Reactions were carried out in two locations (A and B) at a distance of 100 meters from each other from 12:00 to 13:30 on four different days over a month in Bremen.

After 11 days, on October 2, a large difference appeared in the horizontal tubes between the two locations. However, it is important to note that at both location A and location B, the rates between the two horizontal tubes continued to remain the same.

A very important result was obtained 3 days later on October 5, when the rates of hydrolysis in both places in all tubes and directions became practically equal. This could only happen if there was a strong change in the overall solar influence on the Earth, for

example due to the deflection of the solar wind by the interplanetary magnetic field. This is actually proof that the radiation from underground does not exist by itself, but is the result of the solar influence on the Earth.

Four days later, on October 9, a large difference in the rates of hydrolysis and their ratios in the oppositely directed tubes again appeared between locations A and B. But compared to October 5, the ratios between the vertical and horizontal tubes became opposite, and the overall rates decreased significantly.

Thus, in two outdoor locations at the distance of 100 meters between them, the hydrolysis rates and their ratios between the differently directed NMR-tubes are constantly changing within very wide limits on different days. At such a distance, the direct external solar influence cannot be different, so the very different hydrolytic activity of water clusters indicates an underground influence on them, which can only occur under the influence of the Sun. Such indirect solar impact has also a strong influence on the hydrolytic activity of water clusters. What is emitted from underground requires study. It may not only be a stream of particles, but also electromagnetic oscillation, which are also capable of destroying water clusters. For example, we have found that in addition to particles (muons), the hydrolysis of triethyl phosphite in acetonitrile is significantly accelerated by ultraviolet and X-ray radiation.

Materials and methods

Three 5-mm NMR tubes, protected from light by a cardboard screen, were charged with 400 mg of commercial acetonitrile containing 0.02% water. The tubes were oriented vertically, east-west and north-south, and placed outdoors away from large buildings 1 hour before noon. After 30 min, fresh water (7 mg) was added to each tube and mixed briefly by shaking. After 30 min, 25 mg of triethyl phosphite was added and mixed briefly by shaking. The tubes remained protected from light. The reaction rate was determined by measuring the integral intensities of the signals in the ^{31}P -NMR spectra. Experiments were carried out in Bremen, and water was taken from the Weser. NMR-tubes must be from the same manufacturer, they must be tested for identity in this reaction and must not come into contact with other substances. Immediately before use each tube was wiped with a cotton swab soaked in acetonitrile.

Conclusions

As a result of the Sun's impact on the Earth, secondary radiation is constantly formed in the Earth's crust, which is emitted from underground and has a strong influence on the structuring of water molecules and chemical reactivity of water clusters. The intensity of this radiation and its distribution on the Earth's surface are determined by the intensity of solar influence and the features of the geological structure of the Earth's crust in different places and at different geo-

graphic latitudes. This raises new questions. For example, the Earth's crust at the bottom of the oceans is removed from the surface and is thinner than on land. Therefore, the influence of the Sun on hydrolytic processes on the surface of the oceans and on land may differ significantly. Studying this fundamental phenomenon by measuring the hydrolytic activity of water clusters in different places on Earth will allow us to draw conclusions about the processes in the Earth's crust and the nature of underground radiation. This will be of importance for physics, biology, medicine and environmental research.

Competing interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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